

SIMILARITIES AND DISSIMILARITIES IN TERMS OF WORDS FORMATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799555>

Abstract. This article is about how words are formed in Uzbek as well as English languages. In this article we try to analyze the dissimilarities of the construction of words in both languages.

Key words: morphology, lexicology, affixes, conversion, abbreviation, composition, compound words, nominal subject.

СХОДСТВА И РАЗЛИЧИЯ СЛОВООБРАЗОВАНИЯ В УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ.

Аннотация. Эта статья о том, как образуются слова в узбекском и английском языках. В этой статье мы попытаемся проанализировать несхожесть построения слов в обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: морфология, лексикология, аффиксы, конверсия, аббревиатура, состав, сложные слова, именное подлежащее.

Introduction

Morphology and lexicology are two main branches in linguistics and in these two spheres we learn words formation. When people communicate with each other, they utilize words in order to express their thoughts as well as ideas. We can make our speeches more colorful by adding compounds to our dialect. Due to the fact that the popularity of English language in terms of communication in developed as well as developing countries is increasing at an alarm rate, individuals are struggling to learn words formation of this language. And they also try to compare it with their native language`s words formation.

Methods

In this work method of comparative typological analysis is used.

Literature reviews

If we look to the history, there are so many arguments about how to compare the construction of words in two different languages in order to find the differences. Additionally, scholars` classification was distinctive and in some cases it became the foundation knowledge to find out the new one. *In The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language, David Crystal writes about word formations:* "Most English vocabulary arises by making new lexemes out of old ones — either by adding an affix to previously existing forms, altering their word class, or combining them to produce compounds. These processes of construction are of interest to grammarians as well as lexicologists, but the importance of word-formation to the development of the lexicon is second to none. ... After all, almost any lexeme, whether Anglo-Saxon or foreign, can be given an affix, change its word class, or help make a compound. Alongside the Anglo-Saxon root in *kingly*, for example, we have the French root in *royally* and the Latin root in *regally*. There is no elitism here. The processes of affixation, conversion, and compounding are all great levelers."

Ingo Plag explains the process of word formation in Word-Formation in English: "Apart from the processes that attach something to a base (affixation) and processes that do not alter the base (conversion), there are processes involving the deletion of material. English Christian names, for example, can be shortened by deleting parts of the base word, a process also occasionally encountered with words that are not personal names. This type of word formation is called truncation, with the term clipping also being used."

If we talk about word formation, we will try to clarify its meaning, function as well. Word formation is the branch of lexicology that studies two main things. The former is to study the derivative structure of existing words. As for the latter, it studies the patterns on which a language builds new words. And it is also a certain principle of classification of the lexicon. Furthermore, it gives an opportunity to enrich the vocabulary. Mostly, there are two main types of word construction in English language. The first type of them is known as productive which is still used among languages. It is divided into four categories.

- 1) Affixes.
- 2) Conversion
- 3) Abbreviation
- 4) Composition

Prefix as well as suffix are two types of affixes. To be more precise, the former is added to front part of words, while the latter joints end of words. In English prefixes are used regarding to verbs. They always connect to base as they are linked to the independent part of the speech, for instance: "-im" (imbalance), "-mid" (midday). If prefix is used in the objective part of speech, it will be half linked (-over, overprotective). The principal purpose of prefixes is to change the lexical meanings of words, while the focus of suffixes in English language is to make imaginative content.

The second type of word construction is conversion. A conversion is an identifier of word formation in the English language. In addition, it is also known as word making without suffixes. Throughout the history there were many scholars who had many ideas about conversion. For example: Professor A.I. Smirnititsky considered conversion as a morphological method of the word formation. In this case, the word of any fragment moves to another part of speech by exchanging its place with its paradigm. For example, the noun "a dial" refers to the verb "to dial" altering its own paradigm. Conversion can also be morphological-syntactic. Because, in this case, we do not only convert the origin paradigm of word but also exchange its syntactic function too. For instance: "The name of this girl is Anna (in this sentence the noun name`s function is subject). George named his child yesterday (in this sentences the verb to name`s function is predicate). Verbs can be originated with the help of various semantic groups` nouns, that is why, they have different meanings. If it is made by noun which represents part of body, the verb announces the instrument: to eye, to finger and etc. when it is organized through equipment, instruments and descriptive nouns, the verb weapons have the meaning of a tool: to hammer, to nail.

Verbs refer to the actions of living things, which means that nouns are formed by: to mass, to wolf, to monkey. As it is done by the nominal subject, it conveys the meaning of personalization, contributing or devoicing: to fish, to dust, to shell, to paper. Additionally, when verb is made by the noun which expresses place, then the verb will also mean the place: to park, to pocket. If the conversion is counted as the things mentioned above, it will be one of the important word-building

styles. Besides being one of the major way of word-building styles, it also has a huge impact on this effective procedure.

Another type of word formation is abbreviation. It is known as a shortened form of words in sentences. Abbreviation comes from the Latin word `brevis` which means `short`. There are many scientific thoughts about it. One of them is noted by the Linguist David Crystal. He said that abbreviation is not a marginal feature, it is a fundamental component of the English writing system. The largest dictionaries of abbreviation have more than half a million entries and are constantly growing. `Jan` for January can be example of abbreviation. The purpose for reducing some letters of words has both linguistic and extra linguistic hue. It can be used in the purpose of changing the life of people in extra linguistic. There are two main types of abbreviation. They are differentiated with graphic and lexis sides from each other. In graphic way, they are used due to owning less place in the text. They are also divided into several semantic groups. For example: days of weeks (Sun- Sunday), names of month (Jan-January), names of countries (the USA). In lexical way, they are organized by reducing one part of words, for instance: intro- introduction.

With the appearance of composite words, so many syllables appeared in EL undergoes phonetic changes. Compound words can be formed with formulas that belong to a specific period, but with the passage of time the formulas lose their validity. For example, the verb + adverb formula was very effective and numerous words were formed from it: grow up, overturned, but today this structure is not taken into account, in this way productive and word-making ceased. Compound words can be the consequential addition of empty phrases or can happen slowly. It is a semantic isolation. For example: blackboard, daydream, weekend and others. In fact, these words were free phrases and then separated structurally. As a result, these words have lost their meaning before they relate to which part of the sentence separated from the total phrase, specialization of meaning and formed in the form of inseparable word combinations.

In comparison to word formation, word stems help to organize material in word addition. New compound words are made with the help of the combination of word formation and word attachment. If we add affixes to a whole compound word, new compound word will form (for ex: blue-eyed, dress-maker). But, nevertheless, the process of making such words is carried out primarily by adding core. (blue + eye = blue-eyed, dress + make= dressmaker). So, in this case, the main word-forming element of the compound word is the core. In some cases, determining the origin of the construction of words is difficult task. There are some structures for constructing new words. a) core + base; b) core + core + base; c) stem + stem.

Therefore, in terms of morphological structure, not all of compound words are formed by adding word addition. Modern English words formation consists of three the most common structures.

Structures	Examples	New words
1. adjective+noun+ed	Loud+voice+ed	Loud-voiced
2. noun+verb+ing	Hand+clap+ing	Hand clapping
3. noun+verb_er	Party-give-er	partygiver

If the process of differentiating the properties of an object or event is taken into account when forming a compound word, the compound word determines whether words such as a compound word belong to a certain semantic group. Defining the meaning of the word covered is

the second component. For example: mist-covered(town), stone-covered(street), napkin-covered(table).

In these examples, the first component of the compound words defines the word covered by the noun, and in passing to the compound adjective, it clarifies the nature of the whole word.

When forming a compound word, its definition may be specific not only to the second component, but also to the first component, for example, in some compound nouns of the n+n type, the first component can define the second.

English	Uzbek	Russian
Flower-bed	Gulzor	Цветочная клумба
Flower-bud	Gulg`uncha	Цветочная почка
Flower- cup	Gulkosa	Чашечка цветка
Flower- show	Gul ko`rgazma	Выставка цветов
Flower garden	Gulxona	Цветник
Flower pot	Gultuvak	Цветочный горшок
Flower girl	Gul qiz	Цветочница
Flower shop	Gul do`kon	Цветочный магазин

It is clear from the table that the first component “flower” explains the exhibition, pot, shop and etc. in the second component.

To sum up, Therefore, some of the definitions given above cannot fully express the concept of a compound word. In addition, the idea that complex words consist of components with independent meaning cannot be applied to complex words in the Uzbek language. This is related to one or all components of double and repeating words such as nest-nobud, meva-cheva, apak-chapak, and one or more of compound words such as hardamxayol, harkim, sharsharak in the Uzbek language consists of a metaphor or elements that cannot be used independently.

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